

The Arch of Time Arrows – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equations of the new framework of variational manifolds, 8T, it is possible to "unify" the three arrows of time, the radiation arrow, the thermodynamics arrow and the cosmological arrow. In particular, it is possible to analyze the primordial coupling constants series in three different angles, which indicate that the radiation, thermodynamic and cosmological are equivalent, different fingers of the same hand. In that sense the primordial is the arch, which propagate the time arrows.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Is it possible to explain the three "distinct" time arrows using one idea? Author will argue that by using the primorial it is easily within reach. Starting with the radiation arrow, the primorial is perfectly suitable, as we regard the Bosons to be discrete amount of energy or radiation emitted from the lepton. As was presented in the 8T thesis, pages thirty and thirty-one, the time arrow is evident. That is because each coupling term is weaker than the preceding given by the ratio of net to total pair averages. The direction of the arrow is the direction of time.

$$\frac{1}{9} > \frac{3}{30} > \frac{5}{128} > \frac{7}{850} \dots$$

$$\underline{0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots} \rightarrow$$

We already have the radiation arrow and the cosmological arrow unified by the primorial. Now the last arrow, the thermodynamics arrow. How can we present the idea of thermodynamics within the context of the primorial? As one believes, there are several ways to do just that. Among the set of potential ideas, we can state that as the primorial has more options, meaning more distinct primes will be propagated over time. That is because the direction of the arrow is the direction of time. so, over time we have more and more distinct elements, alongside constant matter creation given b equation (1.48), the result of such framework seems to be with an agreement with the second law of thermodynamics and therefore with the thermodynamics arrow. We can use functors to present that idea in rigor;

For simplicity sake, we can use a setting of a partitioned set:

$\mathfrak{U}: Top \rightarrow \text{set}$

$$\Sigma: \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0, \sum_{i=1}^K Z_i \sum_{i=1}^K N_{V_i} = Z_1 N_{V_1} \dots Z_K N_{V_K}, t_1 \right] \quad (2.17)$$

The set in equation (2.17) includes all the arbitrary variations that appeared on the manifold, all the net curvature classes according to their kind, given by the index summation, and according to the amount of times each appeared, given by the scalar multiples $Z_1 \rightarrow Z_K$. At later continuation of time, according to the primorial, we will find that the new set is presented by (2.17.1):

$$\Psi: \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N+\Delta N} \delta g_i = 0, \sum_{i=1}^{K+\Delta K} Z_i \sum_{i=1}^{K+\Delta K} N_{V_i} = Z_1 N_{V_1} \dots Z_K N_{V_K}, t_1 + \Delta t \right] \quad (2.17.1)$$

$$\Delta N, \Delta K \in \mathbb{R}$$

In other words, more matter was created, the number of non-vanishing distinct curvature increased, and their kind increased as well. We have more elements of distinct kind. That does not contradict the flatness, as those are getting weaker and weaker; the point of the above equations is to present the thermodynamic picture in a simple way, which intersect with the Primorial. The primorial is the arch, which according to the 8T propagate all the three time arrows. Radiation are the Bosons, the cosmological is given by the ratios, and the TM arrow is given by the rise of entropy at infinitesimal time increments, these are different fingers of the same hand.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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